

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE *MONAESSES* SPECIES OF SOUTH AFRICA

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DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. (2020). The Thomisidae of South Africa (A-Mo). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: Part 1 Version 1: 1-62. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513274>

NOTE: For species like *M. pustulosus* and *M. paradoxus* you need to examine genitalia

1. *Monaeses austrinus* Simon, 1910

2. *Monaeses fuscus* Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984

3. *Monaeses gibbus* Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984

4. *Monaeses griseus* Pavesi, 1897

5. *Monaeses paradoxus* Lucas, 1864

6. *Monaeses pustulosus* Pavesi, 1895

7. *Monaeses quadrituberculatus* Lawrence, 1927

TMARUS/MONAESES

Species of *Tmarus* and *Monaeses* often closely resemble each other in colour and general behaviour.

However in *Tmarus* species the posterior median eyes are situated nearer to each other than to the posterior lateral eyes, whereas in *Monaeses* the posterior median eyes are nearer to the posterior lateral eyes.

Tmarus species are also distinguished by the shape of the abdomen which often has a tubercle caudodorsally, a character which is mostly absent from *Monaeses* species.